

Metadata Revision and Collection

The Approaches and Input Forms Suggestion

Technical Report, Version 1.0.

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1. Introduction

Knowledge graphs (KGs) use a graph-based data model to manage and extract value from diverse data sources at scale. The 'Literature Information Systems' (LIS) team at DIPF aims to develop an education-focused knowledge graph and establish an Edu Knowledge Graph Lab. The initial KG focuses on events like academic activities and courses, serving as a framework for experimenting with Semantic Web principles. This is part of the 'Exploration project Linked Open Data of Events Calendar at IZB,' which explores implementing a knowledge graph for DIPF's Event Calendar. A current implementation based on LAMP architecture runs internally.

In the accepted scenario, we extend the existing application layer while retaining the current components. We modify administrative web forms and backend functionality for the DBS (Deutscher Bildungsserver) Event Calendar CMS to accommodate new data requirements. At the technical layer, a separate host machine is provisioned with an RDF Graph Database that supports SPARQL endpoints. This platform serves as the hub for event data dissemination, providing access to both internal and external stakeholders.

The construction of the graph involves periodic transfers of data from the SQL Event Database to the RDF Graph Database host system. This is a process implemented by an RDF Data Pipeline component that maps event attributes to Semantic Web vocabularies. The RDF Graph Database content is purged and replaced with each update cycle, ensuring consistent data representation [2].

The existing schema of the Event Calendar database needs enhancement using the Semantic Web approach, with data being incorporated into the Knowledge Graph. Structured data can be transformed into KGs through semantic integration.

The previous technical report describes the process of designing the Event Calendar ontology, the conceptual approach, the methodology used for metadata mappings, and the ontology itself [2]. The report also presents the adaptation and enhancement of the AEON ontology [3], based on BFO [1]. The report describes three scenarios that illustrate the journey toward achieving interoperability and reusability, the project's primary outcomes.

This report provides a technical description of the steps required to implement the ETL pipeline for the Event Calendar project at DIPF. In the Event Calendar Project, the following steps are required:

1. Mediate and Confirm the Metadata Schema Change.
2. Update the DBS database schema to implement changes.
3. Update DBS PHP-Backend code related to changes (IT department).

This report presents the first two steps.

2. Mediate and Confirm the Metadata Schema Change

Several meetings with stakeholders concluded with an improved schema, developed by comparing it with the actual schema and the DBS workflow. The following modifications were accepted:

- Separation of event type – in academic and practical
- Topics separation in concordance with the event type (topic will be chosen from a controlled vocabulary, one list for academic event, one list for practical event)

- The event format is separated by the event type (ex, conference, symposium for academic event, information session, job fair, etc, for practical event)
- Separate metadata for the attendance mode (online, in person, hybrid)
- Audience is necessary only for the practical event
- The possibility of dealing with multiple organizations as event organizers (suggesting organizers)
- Possibility to add an organizer as a person, together with email and/or telephone number
- Keywords from a controlled vocabulary
- The ontology allows for other optional entities:
 - Event Series, sub-events of an event
 - External identifiers DOI, Wikidata, GND, ORCID.
 - Acronym – might be helpful in the context of identifiers
 - Acronyms are handy for event series.
 - Possibility to add an organizer as a person, together with email and/or telephone number.

3. Update the DBS database schema to implement changes

3.1. Separation of event type – in academic and practical

DBS original:

Art der Veranstaltung

Change the place and becomes the first line in the input form

Art der Veranstaltung*

Allowed values: [Wissenschaftliche Veranstaltung \(Academic\)](#)
[Praxisveranstaltung \(Practical\)](#)

3.2. Topics separation in concordance with the event type

DBS original: **Inhaltsbereich der Veranstaltung***

Allgemeinbildung
 Kindertageseinrichtungen
 Vorschule
 Primarstufe
 Sekundarstufe I
 Sekundarstufe II
 Sonderschule/Förderschule

Inhaltsbereich wissenschaftliche Veranstaltung **NEW**

Historische Bildungsforschung Allgemeine Erziehungswissenschaft Empirische Bildungsforschung Schulpädagogik
 Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik Sozialpädagogik Pädagogik der frühen Kindheit
 Erwachsenenbildung / Weiterbildung Pädagogische Freizeitforschung und Sportpädagogik
 Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung in der Erziehungswissenschaft Medienpädagogik Umweltpädagogik
 Differentielle Erziehungs- und Bildungsforschung Hochschulforschung und Hochschuldidaktik Pädagogische Psychologie
 Bildungssoziologie Bildungs- und Erziehungsphilosophie Fachdidaktiken Sonstige
 Bildungsorganisation / Bildungsplanung und Bildungsrecht
 Interkulturelle und International Vergleichende Erziehungswissenschaft

DBS original: **Inhaltsbereich der Veranstaltung***

Allgemeinbildung
 Kindertageseinrichtungen
 Vorschule
 Primarstufe
 Sekundarstufe I
 Sekundarstufe II
 Sonderschule/Förderschule

Inhaltsbereich Praxisveranstaltung **NEW**

Allgemeinbildung Frühe Bildung/Vorschule Primarstufe Sekundarstufe I Sekundarstufe II
 Sonderschule/Förderschule Berufliche Bildung Außerschulische Jugendarbeit Erwachsenenbildung/Weiterbildung
 Lebenslanges Lernen Inklusion/Behindertenpädagogik Soziale Arbeit/Sozialpädagogik Digitalisierung
 Hochschulforschung/ -didaktik/ -bildung Bildungspolitik/ -verwaltung

3.3. The event format is separated in accordance with the event type

DBS original:

Art der Veranstaltung

Art der Veranstaltung Wissenschaftliche Veranstaltung **NEW**

Art der Veranstaltung Praxisveranstaltung **NEW**

3.4. Separate metadata for the attendance mode

Teilnahmeart*

Select

In person

online

hybrid

NEW

3.5. Audience is necessary only for the practical event

DBS original: **Adressaten***

Allgemeine Öffentlichkeit
Eltern
Schüler/-innen
Lehrer/-innen
Studierende
Ausbilder/-innen
Hochschullehrer/innen / Forscher/-innen

Adressanten
Praxisveranstaltung*

Allgemeine Öffentlichkeit Eltern Studierende Bibliotheks- und Dokumentationsfachkräfte
 Fachleute aus Bildungspolitik und -verwaltung Frühpädagogische Fachkräfte Auszubildene
 Weiterbildungsinteressierte Schüler:innen / Kinder / Jugendliche Lehrer:innen Ausbilder:innen
 Hochschullehrer:innen / Forscher:innen Lehrerbildner:innen Erwachsenenbildner:innen
 Behindertenpädagogen:pädagoginnen Sozialpädagogen:-pädagoginnen Journalisten:Journalistinnen

3.6. Keywords from a controlled vocabulary

DBS original:

Schlagwörter*

Schreiben Sie hier

Geographical keywords will be removed. Keywords chosen from a controlled vocabulary (FID) with autocomplete. Also allows for free keywords.

Schlagwörter*

× Digitale Medien × Digitalisierung × Open Educational Resources × Digitale Bildung × FOE21 × OER × zeitgemäße Bildung
× Forum Open Education × Open Knowledge

3.7. Optional: Event Series

An event series could be added as a separate entity (new). Further, all events belonging to the event series should be added. Allows an additional identifier from external sources like [Wikidata](#), GND, and DOI.

Necessary metadata:

The screenshot shows a form with the following fields:

- Veranstaltungsreihe***: Text input containing "ECER-EERA".
- Art der Veranstaltung***: Dropdown menu with options "Scientific event", "Scientific event", and "Practice-oriented event".
- Akronyme***: Text input containing "ECER".
- Kurzbeschreibung**: Text input containing "Event series in education".
- Veranstaltungen***: Dropdown menu with options "Select", "ECER_2011", and "ECER_2012".
- Externer Identifikator**: Two text input fields containing "https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q17012621" and "https://doi.org/10.1000/1820.1000/182".

3.8. Optional: Events connected to an Event Series Entity.

An event series could be added as a separate entity (new). Further, all events belonging to the event series should be added.

The Event Series Entity should already be created in a previous step.

Necessary metadata:

The screenshot shows a form with the following field:

- Veranstaltungsreihe**: Dropdown menu with options "Select", "ECER-EERA", "MTSR", and "OTHER SERIES". The "ECER-EERA" option is highlighted in green.

3.9. The possibility of dealing with multiple organizations as Organizers

- Organizers could be a string for a small institution or group of people, or a person who is not in the DBS database of institutions (https://www.bildungserver.de/institutionen_de.html). First, the organizer should be suggested from the DBS institutions list.
- If there is a person as an organizer, the fields “name of the contact person from the organizer” and “phone number of the organizer” will be used.

DBS original:

Veranstalter*

Allows multiple choices as separate entities. The values will be suggested by the organizers ' list.

Veranstalter*:

× Bündnis Freie Bildung × Open Knowledge Foundation Deutschland e. V. × Wikimedia Deutschland e. V.

If the organizer is an institution, it will be chosen from the DBS list of institutions. Multiple values are allowed.

If the organizer is a person, add name and telephone/email.

Metadata:

Veranstalter*

Di

DIPF

Direktor.....

Diplomate.....

Veranstalter (Person Kontaktname)* Sylvia Schneider

Veranstalter(Person KontaktTel/email) s.schneider@example.de

3.10. Other optional elements

- **External identifiers:** Identifiers for events are sought, so ROR-ID is probably not expedient; instead, the GND-ID should be included. WikidataID, GND-ID, and DOI are only at the Event Series level. External identifiers are labeled with explanations. Optional, repetitive field if necessary.
- **Event fee:** In the AEON ontology, this data is modeled as a numerical value. DBS is in favor of "yes/no" implementation. If "yes", it is unclear which numerical value this should map to; a workaround would be necessary. The final decision is in favor of Schema.org, which will be used in place of it. In the form, the status does not change from the actual status.

4. Conclusion and Outlook

This technical report presents the agreed modifications to the schema and the actual workflow of DBS. The next step is to be implemented by the IT team.

As evolving organisms, a schema and an ontology are subject to continuous revision and improvement; for this reason, the current concepts and relations may change organically over time. Therefore, the current report will be updated when necessary.

As part of this report, an Excel file containing the updated metadata list is attached.

References

- [1] Arp, R., Smith, B., Spear, A. D. Building Ontologies with Basic Formal Ontology (Mit Press, 2015)
- [2] Veja, C., Schindler, C.: The Event Calendar Ontology. The Approaches and Mappings. Technical Report, v2.0. (2024)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10423581>
- [3] Strömert, P.: AEON - Die Academic Event Ontology. Zenodo (2021), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4629629>